

A View of the Instructional Challenges in the New Face-to-Face Class Mode: Kindergarten Teachers in Focus

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Abstract. This study explored the lived experiences, challenges encountered, coping mechanisms, and insights of kindergarten teachers in public elementary schools on the instructional challenges they faced in the face-to-face classes modality. The participants were coming from the Schools of Arakan, West District, Division of Cotabato, DepEd Region XII. There were ten (10) teachers who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas from the participants. The participants were purposely selected as representatives from the group of kindergarten teachers who are assigned in the same District. The in-depth interview was employed to gather significant information with regard to their respective lived experiences. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged pertaining to their lived experiences: concretizing the learners' socialization skills, considering health protocols and hurdling work stress. There were three sub-themes that emerged from the challenges or work fatigue by the participants. These are multiple workloads, worries getting sick and the academic problems. The two coping mechanisms of teachers as participants in the challenges they experienced were creating personality improvement interventions and continuous improvement in the new normal. The three educational management insights drawn from the participants were work-life balance, obeying safety protocols and the importance of hybrid learning. Thus, DepEd may motivate and assist their teachers by evaluating their workloads and endorsing their endeavors to tackle educational deficiencies in schools. Additionally, they may establish a comprehensive initiative or initiative to enhance the skills and expertise of teachers, enabling them to effectively and efficiently carry out both in-person classes and alternative teaching methods in schools.

KEY WORDS

1. Instructional Challenges 2. Lived Experiences 3. Kindergarten Teachers

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1. Introduction

During the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic, the field of education experienced serious negative consequences. While this global emergency is still ongoing, it has presented significant concerns to nations across the globe, encompassing both developed and developing regions. The widespread impact of these devel-

opments has resulted in significant disruptions and detrimental effects across various domains of society. According to Chua (2022), the economic sector in the Philippines experiences an annual estimated loss of approximately 1.4 trillion pesos. Globally speaking, the closure of face-to-face schools in the education sector has

resulted in a substantial long-term economic impact, with an estimated loss of 11 trillion pesos per year. This reduction in productivity is projected to have lasting effects over the next four decades. In addition to this, there exists a decline in learning outcomes due to the utilization of online learning, which has been found to be approximately 52 percent effective according to a study conducted in the United States (Dorn et al., 2020). Furthermore, the effectiveness of modular learning, a specific approach within online learning, is even lower, estimated to be around 37 percent (Chua, 2022). These estimations were calculated based on the most favorable circumstances. These conditions encompass factors such as the involvement of parents and tutors, the ability of pupils to engage in self-directed learning, the availability of resources and technology, and several other advantageous circumstances. Therefore, it is possible that underprivileged children may experience significantly reduced learning gains, and in some cases, even negative learning outcomes. With these cited, numerous organizations, including NEDA, UNICEF, parents, and private school sectors, have collectively appealed to the national government to deliberate on the resumption of educational institutions inside the country (Chua, 2022; UNICEF, 2021; Bayod et al., 2021). According to Bryant, Dorn, Hall, and Panier (2020), there was a belief that the reopening of schools will play a role in the recovery strategy by offering crucial social support, particularly to pupils who are vulnerable. Additionally, Gopez (2021) argued that reopening schools would help restore a sense of normalcy. According to the citation, the Philippines stands out among the ASEAN countries as the sole nation in the area to have implemented an extended closure of schools lasting over a year. In December 2021, the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd) made the decision to implement a phased approach in the reopening of schools, commencing with a selection of 150 pilot schools around the nation. Subsequently, other educational institutions were incorporated into the expansion stage of the pilot initiative. During the period of October 2021, a series of pilot face-to-face classes were implemented in the Bangsamoro region, encompassing a total of 33 schools (MBHTE, 2021). Recent reports on the reintroduction of face-to-face classes for the 2022-2023 school year have created enthusiasm, but the reappearance of COVID-19 cases has sparked concern. It is a well-known truth that the fundamental goals of schools are to instruct children to study and learn; hence, teachers are accountable for affecting students' academic performance. Now that the distant arrangement will no longer be an impediment to learning, some teachers and students feel extra pressure to perform well in a face-to-face environment. It is hoped that school officials will not place undue demands on students, instructors, and staff, given that everyone's physical, mental, and psychological health has suffered from two years of distance learning and classes. The process of resuming classes in the context of the "new normal" necessitates extensive preparations, since educational institutions participating in the pilot implementation of face-to-face instruction must adhere to the School Safety Assessment (SSAT). This assessment serves as a comprehensive guideline established by the inter-agency task force responsible for ensuring the safe reopening of schools, as outlined in the Philippine Joint Memorandum Circular 1, S. 2021. The approach to the resumption of educational activities is founded upon the principle of collective obligations. Further, additional government entities have made a commitment to provide schools with resources and technical support. Stringent preparations are necessary in order to guarantee the safety of both school children and workers during their physical attendance at school. It is imperative for governmental authorities and educational administrators to prioritize the establishment of a school reopen-

ing strategy that fosters a return to normalcy, while also mitigating the risk of exacerbating the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. Nevertheless, the formidable challenge is with educators and other school staff who are at the forefront of the process of rebuilding educational institutions. In conjunction with the requisite physical and safety measures, the Philippine Department of Education has underscored the imperative of schools offering psychological first aid (PFA) to facilitate the transition of students from a two-year period of remote learning to in-person classroom instruction. Nevertheless, due to the limited availability of PFA providers within educational institutions (Manza et al., 2021), teachers are required to assume the responsibility of delivering these services alongside their instructional obligations. According to UNICEF (2021), educators serving on the front lines of education are currently under stress as a result of

the COVID-19 pandemic. This stress has the potential to impact the overall well-being of their children. The aforementioned phenomenon is also evident and documented in Arakan, West District, which is located in Cotabato Division, Region XII. As educational institutions continue to strategize for the implementation of full-time, in-person instruction, it is important to acknowledge the potential challenges faced by our dedicated teachers on the front lines. The dearth of research on school reopening tactics further contributes to our constrained comprehension of the optimal methods by which educational institutions can effectively adapt to the current circumstances. Therefore, the researcher posited the necessity of investigating the experiences and problems faced by teachers in order to provide valuable insights into the efficacy of face-to-face classes in the new normal.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This background inspired the researcher to conduct a qualitative study on the lived experiences, encountered instructional challenges, coping methods, and management insights of elementary school teachers one year after the resumption of face-to-face sessions in public elementary schools. Notably, there are few research and literary works on face-to-face schooling in the Philippines during the pandemic that focus on teachers' experiences at the primary level. The majority of international research has focused on the introduction of face-to-face classes in high school and higher education. In addition, the findings of this study may serve as a basis for policymakers, school administrators, and teachers to enhance their processes and practices in relation to the full implementation of face-to-face lessons during the post-pandemic, as well as a basis for future local empirical research. Consequently, this work is deemed to be of great significance.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are the instructional challenges of kindergarten teachers in the new face-to-face classes mode?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of kinder teachers in the instructional challenges encountered in the new face-to-face classes mode?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms are conceptually and operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Face-to-face classes –often known as traditional education, entail the dissemination of course

content and learning materials to a collective cohort of students through direct, in-person interaction. This facilitates real-time engagement between a student and an instructor, representing the most traditional method of educational

pedagogy. Furthermore, students benefit from enhanced engagement with their classmates. In the context of traditional classroom instruction, students are expected to take responsibility for their academic progress within the confines of scheduled class sessions. The utilization of face-to-face training has been found to enhance students' understanding and retention of course content, while also fostering the development of interpersonal connections among class participants. The style of instruction known as face-to-face learning is predominantly concentrated around the teacher and exhibits significant variations across different cultures. Numerous contemporary educational systems have largely forsaken traditional in-person modes of instruction in order to cater to the unique needs and preferences of individual pupils. Lived Experiences refer to teacher participants first-hand observations, gained knowledge and practical contact with the facts and events related to the full im-

1.4. Significant of the Study—To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education (DepED) Teachers. The DepEd, particularly the schools of the Division of Cotabato to look into their face-to-face classes implementations and instructional practices like trainings and enhancement activities to help the teachers in handling face-to-face classes in these challenging times. This study shall provide information on the real situation of the public secondary school teachers with regards to their work experiences and face-to-face issues in the new normal. School Principals and Headteachers. For the school principals and school, heads to gain a clear understanding of teachers' challenges faced in their respective stations in relation to the full resumption of the face-to-face classes in public secondary

plementation of the face-to-face classes after a year of implementation in public elementary schools. These include their feelings and understanding on their role as teachers and program implementers of the Department of Education in the new normal. Challenges and Difficulties refer to the weaknesses, limitations, hindrances, issues, problems and other negative experiences encountered by the teacher-participants in terms of their instructional activities in the the face-to-face classes in public elementary schools. Coping Mechanisms refer to the coping strategies and initiatives provided by the Department of Education and the personal coping strategies of teachers themselves on the challenges they encountered in the full implementation of the face-to-face classes in public elementary schools Insights refer to the academic and management lessons learned by the elementary teachers in their overall experiences, positive or negative.

schools. This may also serve as their basis for future capacity enhancement programs related to handling face-to-face classes amidst the pandemic. Teachers. The findings of the study shall provide the scenario as to how teachers are challenged to create and conduct instructional activities in face-to-face classes in the new normal. The study may share its lessons learned to other teachers who are experiencing the same issues and problems, if there are any. Future researchers. This study also provides research literature which could also serve as basis for future researchers who would wish to conduct a study parallel to the themes of this study and or applying other categories that their study will cover. The study could be a strong basis especially for those who will engage in qualitative research employing phenomenology or in other words, this would serve as reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—This study is based on the Behaviorist learning theory, specifically the Direct Instruction approach, which was created in the 1960s and emphasizes the needs of children in face-to-face instructional settings. According to the behaviorist learning theory, Direct Instruction employs a method wherein every learning task is deconstructed into its most basic elements, necessitating the attainment of proficiency in simpler skills prior to progressing to more challenging assignments. In the educational setting, students are organized into cohorts based on their individual levels of academic attainment. Instructors are equipped with meticulously crafted instructional outlines, ensuring clarity and coherence in their teaching approach. Students actively engage in the learning process by participating in verbal interactions with the teacher as well as collectively as a group. Progression within the group is contingent upon the attainment of mastery by all individuals, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. An integral element of the Model entails the utilization of small group training inside a physical, in-person environment. Recent research findings indicate that the implementation of rapid-fire, teacher-led, small-group training yields superior outcomes compared to individualized instruction. Additionally, it places significant emphasis on the development of oral communication abilities, a crucial aspect for students hailing from socioeconomically disadvantaged backgrounds and houses where English is not the primary language. Furthermore, students have the potential to function as role models for their peers and participate in iterative practice. The objective of employing direct instruction within small group settings is to effectively prompt a substantial level of participation from students, a process that is helped through the utilization of unison or choral answers. This facilitates increased engagement in practicing various skills and enables instructors to provide more regular feedback on the development of individual students. Furthermore, the significance of providing remedial criticism is emphasized. According to Stromer's (1975) findings, the implementation of corrections, which involve displaying the correct reaction after an error has occurred, along with the use of differentiated praise, leads to a reduction in errors. In general, the instructor's delivery of significant variables was expeditious and diverse. The pace and corrective measures employed in Direct Instruction can significantly influence students' academic advancement and their level of involvement inside the classroom. The Department of Education (DepEd) has recently disclosed the guidelines for the school calendar and extracurricular activities for the upcoming academic year of 2023-2024, aligning with its commitment to restore five days of face-to-face education. The declaration of the commencement and conclusion dates for the academic year has been officially endorsed by Vice President and Secretary Sara Z. Duterte through the signing of the Department of Education (DepEd) order. As per the order, courses are scheduled to commence on August 22 and conclude on July 7, 2023. The academic year will consist of 203 teaching days, subject to potential adjustments in the event of unanticipated circumstances that necessitate modifications to the school calendar. The Department of Education (DepEd) also offers guidance and instruction for the resumption of classes and the phased reintroduction of five days of face-to-face educational activities that started in 2022. In line with the guidelines outlined in Department Order 034, specifically section 2022, the reopening of schools and the resumption of five (5) days of in-person classes can be achieved by ensuring adherence to the customary pre-pandemic regulatory permits and licenses, as mandated by relevant legislation or local ordinances. The Department of Education (DepEd) has made recommendations for educational institutions to implement a combination of in-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

person instruction, blended learning, and full remote learning for a period extending until October 31, 2022. Last November 2, 2022, it was mandated that all public and private educational institutions transition to a schedule of five days of in-person instruction. In accordance with DO 21, s. 2019 (Policy Guidelines on the K–12 Basic Education Program) and DO 01, s. 2022, it is imperative that any educational institution wishing to adopt remote learning or blended learning must also incorporate alternate delivery modes. Revisions to the Policy Guidelines for the Homeschooling Program. The implementation of the School Calendar and Activities for the academic year 2022-2023, 2023-2024b will adhere to the guidelines set by national primary and secondary educational institutions, en-

compassing both public and private Community Learning Centers (CLCs). The calendar may be employed by private schools, public universities, and community colleges. Furthermore, it should be noted that students have the opportunity to commence their lessons within the time-frame spanning from the first Monday of June to the final day of August. Furthermore, the utilization of Classroom-based and System Assessments, the implementation of the Learning Recovery and Continuity Plan (LRCP), and the execution of the Basic Education Development Plan (BEDP) 2030 are expected to facilitate the efficient implementation of the K-12 Basic Education Program in schools, even in the midst of the COVID-19 epidemic.

2. Methodology

Presented in this chapter is the method. It includes the Philosophical Assumption, Qualitative Assumption, Design and Procedure, Research, Participants, Role of the Researcher, Data Collection, Data Analysis, and Trustworthiness of the Study.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumptions of the study were used in analyzing and interpreting my results.

At its most basic level, psychological research can be used to explain and forecast parts of the human experience, improve our understanding

of the lived experiences of different groups of people, or criticize and change the current conditions in which we live and seek to grow (Lincoln, Lynham, Guba, 2013). According to Creswell (2012), the ontological issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics. Qualitative researchers embrace the idea of multiple realities and report on these multiple realities by exploring multiple forms of evidence from different individuals' perspectives and experiences. Hence, when studying individuals, I as a qualitative researcher conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. With the epistemological assumption, as a researcher, I aim to become as close to the people I am studying as possible. The individual perspectives I gathered from the field research are used to compile subjective evidence. Therefore, conducting a qualitative study means that I tried to get as close as possible to the participants being studied collecting subjective evidences assembled based on individual views. Since epistemology is concerned with providing a philosophical grounding for deciding what kinds of knowledge are possible

and how we can ensure that they are both adequate and legitimate, I was able to discover how knowledge is known, through the subjective experiences of people. These are important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the field or get to know the participants, the more they know what they know from firsthand information (Guba Lincoln, 2008). Qualitative researchers make their values clear in a study, whereas quantitative researchers bring their values to a study. This is the axiological assumption that qualitative research is based on. In this study, I acknowledged the study's value-laden nature and actively reported their values and prejudices, as well as the value-laden nature of field data (Creswell, 2012). Qualitative research processes or rhetoric are described as inductive, emergent, and influenced by my experience gathering and evaluating data. Rather than being handed down wholly from a theory or from the perspectives of the inquirer, the logic I shall follow is inductive, starting from the ground up. During the data analysis, I'll take a step-by-step approach to examine the data in order to gain a more in-depth understanding of the subject at hand.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Individuals want to comprehend their reality and generate their own unique meanings that correlate to their experiences using Social Constructivism as an interpretative framework for qualitative assumptions (Creswell, 2013). These meanings are not imprinted or innate in each person. Rather, meanings emerge as a result of interactions with others (Creswell, 2013). These meanings are varied and multiple, leading the

researcher to look for the complexity of views rather than narrow the meanings into a few categories or ideas. Further, as a researcher, my purpose is to rely as much as possible on the perspectives of the participants. These subjective meanings are frequently disputed in social and historical contexts. In other words, they are developed through interactions with others as well as historical and cultural conventions that work in people's lives, rather than being merely imprinted on them.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—

The study was conducted using a qualitative-inquiry-based phenomenological research design using open-ended questions. Phenomenological research is a kind of investigation in which the researcher identifies the essence of participants' descriptions of a phenomenon. The researcher brackets or sets aside his or her own experiences in order to understand the experiences of the study participants (Creswell Creswell, 2017). The researcher was able to produce a description of the teachers' shared meanings with regard to their experiences in the full resumption of face to face classes while emphasizing the similarity of their experiences (Creswell, 2007). Phenomenological approaches are particularly effective at bringing to the fore individual experiences and perceptions from their own points of view, and so challenging structural or normative assumptions. Adding an interpretive component to phenomenological research allows it to inform, support, or question policy and action by allowing it to be utilized as the foundation for practical theory (Lester et al., 2009). As a result, the research methodology is a good fit for capturing the thoughts and experiences of teachers in an inclusive setting. According to Bogart (2017), gaining a clearer image of the occurrence will aid in filling research gaps and pro-

viding suggestions for improvement, which in the context of the current study refers to teachers' experiences in the classroom. The study attempted to present the "living worlds" of the participants, finally exposing their personal relevance in relation to the experience, as a design that captures the experiences of a "chosen few" addressing specific phenomena. Further, this study also employed participants' observations in an In-Depth Interview (IDI). According to Denzel Lincoln (2000), as cited by Lee (2007) in Pelobello (2015), this method involves the use and collection of variety of interviews, observations, history, interactional and visual texts that describe routines, problems and meaning of individual lives. It is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions that explore a social or human problem. It builds a holistic picture, analyzes words, reports, detailed views of informants, and conducts the study in a natural setting. Furthermore, real life situations need to be explored in terms of their contextual nature as seen by the participants. Therefore, phenomenology is an appropriate and applicable technique to explore the topics on the lived experiences of elementary school teachers public schools. Common themes will be analyzed, coded and extracted from all of the interviews.

2.4. Research Participants—This study was conducted in DepEd Region XII, Division of Cotabato, specifically in Arakan, West District. Only 10 kindergarten teachers as participants from different school and as the key informants were included and were purposely selected based on the nature of their work as classroom teachers and who already experienced working in the Department of Education for at least three years or more. The purposive sampling technique, also called judgment sampling, is the deliberate choice of an informant due to the qualities the informant possesses. Accord-

ing to Bernard (2006), it is a non-random technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of informants. It was the researcher who decided what needs to be known and sets out to find people who can and are willing to provide the information by virtue of knowledge or experience. Purposive sampling is exemplified through the key informant technique wherein one or a few individuals are solicited to act as guides to the phenomenon. Key informants are observant, reflective members of the community of interest who know much about the topic and are both able and willing to share their knowl-

edge. To gain a variance in perspective from participants, the effort was extended to include both male and female as well as individuals with various levels of educational training, attainment and rank. Specifically, the inclusion criteria include the following: (1) Teachers who

have been teaching in the kindergarten or in elementary classrooms for three years or more; (2) had experienced teaching in the old and new normal; and (3) teachers who experienced challenges in the resumption of full face-to-face classes in schools.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation

The participants were adequately informed about the research undertaking through an informed consent. Consent was given freely and the researcher made sure that the participants understood what was being asked and emphasized that their participations were just purely voluntary. All participants were required to provide written informed consent. The potential participants were approached individually online and given an explanation of the purpose of the study and data collection process. They were also given an appropriate time to ask questions and address concerns. It was explained that their participation was voluntary; they may also refuse to participate or withdraw from the study while it was in progress. When the participants agreed to be part of the In-Depth Interview (IDI), a date, time, and venue were set. Anonymity and Confidentiality The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were preserved by not revealing their names and identity in the data collection, analysis and reporting of the study findings. Privacy and confidentiality of the in-

terview environment were managed carefully during the interview sessions, data analysis and dissemination of the findings. The confidentiality of handling the data is in accordance to Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Interview Sessions Each interview was conducted individual through online. The interview was done with the use of google meet, google sheets and messenger application. The researcher was the only knowledgeable person who can match the identity of the participants in voice and in video recordings. In recording the data, interviews were audio-taped and video recorded with the permission of the participants, and the voice records were transcribed verbatimly. Some notes were taken by the researcher to have genuine, accurate and authentic transcription but the identification of the information of the participants were removed or disguised. Further, the interviews, transcriptions and consent forms were kept in a secured location. To safeguard confidentiality, consent forms were stored in a separate location from the other data so there is no way they can be linked to the interviews.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—In qualitative research, the researcher's role is to try to gain access to the needed data while exploring the research participants' ideas and feelings on the phenomenon being studied. This is not a simple task, to say the least. This entails inviting people to discuss topics that are potentially highly personal to them. Reliving prior experiences

might be tough at times when the experiences being explored are somehow negative to them and are still fresh in the participant's thoughts. My first job as a researcher is to protect participants and their data in any method that data is acquired. Participants shall be given explicit and articulated mechanisms for such safeguarding.

2.7. *Data Collection*—In gathering the data, I prepared the interview guide which is composed of three (3) main significant questions which inquired about the experiences of elementary school teachers. A thorough deliberation was made on the aspect of determining the problems of teachers in their effort to become effective and efficient new normal teachers in schools. I made sure that my interview guide was validated by the experts. Moreover, I made sure that all ethical protocols were observed and implemented as I collected the data. An official letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Cotabato, DepEd Division Office, District Supervisor and to the Principal of the Schools asking permission to conduct the study. After receiving the approval letter, the conditions set by the approving authority will be considered and met. Then, the interview sessions followed. The interviews were conducted in public places with private areas to protect confidentiality for some of the participants and since the study was conducted during the pandemic - COVID-19, Facebook Messenger, Google Sheets, Zoom and Google meet were also used to other participants to adhere to the protocols issued by the Department of Health and the Inter-Agency task Force. The interviews were audio recorded with the consent of the participants. In addition, participants were asked to refrain from using names dur-

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then

ing the interview (names of people and places). At each interview, I discussed the purpose of the study, the structure of the interview and the nature, benefits and risks of participation were discussed with the participants. They were, likewise, informed that participation is voluntary and that all the information gathered are held with strict measures of confidentiality. They were informed that there is no financial compensation for their participation and their participation could raise awareness and provide insight on the phenomenon being investigated. Right after, the transcription of In-depth Interviews (IDI) proceedings was done with the help of the note taker and recorder. I also utilized Inscribe software trial version in transcribing the participants' responses and I also ensured the authentic responses of the informants. In the process, I was able to establish rapport with the interviewees to elicit honest and open responses. After the IDI process, I re-stated or summarized the information, then, presented it to them to vouch accuracy. The sharing of findings with the participants allows them to critically analyze and comment on it. The participants also affirmed that the summaries presented to them is an original reflection of their views, feelings, and experiences. In this study, their affirmation on the accuracy and completeness of the information contributed much to the credibility of the study. The data gathered from the IDI were organized accordingly into themes for analysis.

finds statements about how individuals were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of

“how” the experience happened. This was called “structural description,” and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it’s a flexible method which can be used both for explorative studies, where the researcher does not have a clear idea of what patterns are being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher knows exactly what he or she is interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and tries to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods

study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation - The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned were the use of environmental triangulation best suited the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—According to Braun and Clark (2006) methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomeno-

logical analysis (IPA) and methods which are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different

theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data

by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as develop by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful tome in the process of coding, sorting and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedure included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with coded being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—For trustworthiness of the study, I adhered to credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability of qualitative study. Credibility. This is defined as the confidence that can be placed in the truth of the research findings. Credibility

establishes whether the research findings represent plausible information drawn from the participants’ original data and is a correct interpretation of the participants’ original views. One of the key criteria addressed by researchers is that of internal validity, in which they seek to

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

ensure that their study measures or tests what is actually intended. Guba and Lincoln (2009) argue that ensuring credibility is one of most important factors in establishing trustworthiness. In this study, credibility was considered during the interview process and even in the analysis of data. I made sure that the responses of the participants were transcribed verbatim without adding to or rephrasing their answers. Transferability. The term "transferability" refers to the extent to which the results of one study can be applied to a variety of circumstances (Silverman, 2001). The concern with positivist work is typically establishing that the results of the study at hand can be applied to a larger population. It is impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions of a qualitative study are relevant to other contexts and populations since qualitative findings are specialized to a small number of specific environments and individuals. Many naturalists feel that even conventional generalizability is impossible in practice since all observations are characterized by the individual situations in which they are made. Dependability. In this study, I used ap-

proaches to address the issue of reliability. to demonstrate that comparable results would be reached if the work was redone using the same procedures and circumstances. Guba and Lincoln (2008) emphasize the interconnectedness between credibility and dependability, stating that demonstrating the former goes a long way toward assuring the latter. This can be accomplished by combining tactics such as individual interviews to purposively selected different individuals. Confirmability. The qualitative investigator's concept of confirmability and objectivity is a similar concern. In order to lessen the influence of bias, the importance of giving back and sharing the results to the participants in promoting such confirmability was highlighted once more to satisfy this part. The extent to which the researcher confesses his or her own predispositions, according to Miles and Huberman, is a significant factor for confirmability. In the study, part of the steps in analyzing the data were taken to ensure that the conclusions of the study are the result of the informants' experiences and thoughts, rather than my personal ideologies, qualities and preferences.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and their answers based on the responses of the participants of the study. The participants revealed their lived experiences as they discern their first-hand experiences in the full implementation of the face-to-face classes in public elementary schools. The participants' challenges encountered, coping mechanisms and insights were also presented in this part of the research specifically in Arakan, West District, Division of Cotabato, DepEd Region XII. In this chapter, the results of the thematic analysis are presented. It is followed by discussions arranged according to themes and subthemes that were generated.

3.1. The instructional challenges of kindergarten teachers in the new face-to-face classes mode—In analyzing the instructional challenges of the public kinder teachers in the new face of face-to-face classes mode, their lived experiences as a whole must be considered first. Based on the interview answers shared by the teachers themselves (P1-P10), I was able

to identify three (3) major themes. These are: concretizing the learners' socialization skills, considering health protocols and hurdling work stress. The kinder teachers have shared diverse and demanding yet valuable experiences in educating students in schools. The majority of these experiences are rich in learning opportunities, which they consider as the driving force

behind their successful management of teaching and learning processes in their respective schools. The majority of individuals referred to Traditional (Face-to-Face) training, also known as in-person (F2F) instruction, as focusing on various elements including lectures, capstone projects, group projects, laboratories, studios, and similar activities. Synchronous instruction

3.1.1. Concretizing the learners' socialization skills—Due to the proliferation of social media and computer technology, Filipino learners are increasingly reducing their in-person interactions and devoting significantly more time to screen-based activities. Consequently, the decline in socialization throughout critical developmental stages has already occurred, impacting the development of communication skills. The ongoing pandemic has exacerbated the issue by cultivating an isolated learning environment. Given the various challenges at hand, it is plausible that the cohort of children affected by COVID-19 may persist in lagging behind in acquiring essential interpersonal, interpersonal, and nonverbal communication skills. These skills are vital for engaging with people and establishing meaningful connections throughout our lifetimes. Individuals who are currently restricted to their houses have become accustomed to solitude, mostly engaging with electronic devices, resulting in less interactions with their immediate environment. As a result, a theme emerged that centered around teachers prioritizing the development of learners' socialization skills. As narrated by participant 1, she has been compelled to devise strategies for doing in-person instruction within the pandemic while prioritizing the well-being of all individuals involved. Despite the challenges, she has acquired valuable knowledge and developed innovative teaching resources. Despite the difficulties, she has been greatly impressed by the resilience and perseverance demonstrated by the

is delivered in a physical learning setting, where all students are present simultaneously, adhering to the required safety measures. The direct interaction among students, teachers, and their peers is a significant advantage of the traditional classroom setting. Both the instructor and the other students act as sources of inspiration for the teachers.

students, staff, and parents. She took into account her learners' sociability skills as she has been frequently noting that many of her learners were already exhibiting a deficiency in confidence when it comes to participating in group settings. P5 shared that she has been required to employ unconventional thinking and devise inventive strategies to maintain her pupils' interest and ensure optimal educational outcomes. Her main objective this time was to instruct them in the art of proficiently interacting with others. P6 added that the scenario has cultivated a heightened level of cooperation among his colleagues, his students, and their parents. Students have deficiencies in socialization skills, necessitating his efforts to enhance their ability to engage with others and cultivate friendships. The outcome of the study is linked to Watermeyer et al.'s (2020) concept that less pupil connection due to physical separation reduces learning motivation and passion. The absence of genuine interpersonal contacts leads to decreased motivation and disconnection. Authentic engagement between students and teachers in the classroom leads to positive psychological well-being, increased motivation, and a heightened sense of belonging. Furthermore, the proximate campus surroundings have an impact on students' drive, welfare, self-perception, and academic success. In their study, Kahu and Nelson (2018) examine the impact of budgeting assistance, psychological support, and life skills classes on the health and academic performance of students. The setting was not conducive to student interaction.

3.1.2. Considering health protocols—The government’s strategy to progressively bring back the in-person instruction in schools nationwide has been reinforced by the recent decrease of COVID-19 cases, fostering a feeling of hopefulness. Even with the complete integration of classes in schools. However, some educators have substantial challenges when it comes to giving in-person classes and being physically present on-site for a variety of reasons. Educators have expressed concern about the limited time frame available to meet the various educational demands of kids. Several instructors have also stated that they have limited teaching and learning resources. There are apprehensions regarding the readiness of students for face-to-face training. The teachers faced challenges in maintaining student engagement in both conventional classroom environments and self-directed teaching modalities. Like the students, teachers also reported difficulties in perceiving their pupils’ auditory cues due to the use of facial masks and shields. Currently, teachers instruct with constraints in every area. Notwithstanding the obstacles they encountered, P3 shared that she had a positive outlook regarding the advancements they can achieve in this novel educational setting. She had faith in the tenacity and flexibility of both educators and learners where they consistently adhere to safety measures. P4 added that the responsibility of safeguarding the safety and well-being of all pupils in the classroom is accompanied by a specific amount of concern. The health procedures are strict, and adhering to them is essential yet anxiety-provoking. P6 concluded that occasionally, the alterations and difficulties

3.1.3. Hurdling work stress—Creating a favorable learning atmosphere in the classroom is crucial. Individuals who persisted with face-to-face training during the epidemic created and followed regulations to uphold the safety

can be daunting. Managing the implementation of novel pedagogical approaches, ensuring adherence to safety measures, and addressing the emotional well-being of pupils is a formidable undertaking. However, he constantly reinforced the significance of his position and the influence he exerted on the lives of his students. This finding is connected to the discoveries made by Hlescu et.al. (2020) that students acquire knowledge through the process of observing others, physically engaging with equipment during practical activities, manipulating information, and inquiring by asking questions. Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, practical assignments were shifted to virtual classrooms. In order to adapt to remote and distance teaching methods, instructors often assigned practical tasks in virtual classrooms, striving to create an engaging environment. Students will have the opportunity to see presentations, films, and pictures, with the potential for concurrent evaluation. In addition, during practical activities, students acquire knowledge through the process of interpreting and observing actual actions performed by their peers. Prior to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, children had the opportunity to engage in kinesthetic learning through their active involvement in hands-on activities. Furthermore, pupils acquired knowledge not only through tactile experiences but also through their careful observations and meaningful interactions. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, students have limited opportunities to engage in physical interactions with their learning activities and materials. However, according to Biggs and Tang (2011), effective learning requires the engagement of several sensory modalities such as auditory, tactile, visual, verbal, and olfactory.

of in-person educational sessions. Seldom did these procedures yield the anticipated outcomes. There is a correlation between postponing graduation and strictly enforcing minimal distancing criteria, which leads to worse scores on na-

tional student experience surveys. The physical distancing of pupils, which naturally caused discomfort for those transitioning from their former setting, had a substantial adverse effect on student learning and the process of creating meaning. Teachers employ these strategies to seek resolutions and carry out several responsibilities in the classroom, resulting in weariness and stress. P3 explained that she possessed a profound comprehension of her students' emotional requirements, particularly in the midst of these arduous circumstances. This allowed her to offer the essential assistance and established a supportive educational setting that encourages progress and advancement. During her return to in-person classes, she was confronted with a greater amount of tasks and responsibilities. At times, she found it stressful to ensure compliance with safety rules while developing lesson plans and supervising both online and offline students. Nevertheless, she was dedicated to effectively handling this augmented workload and ensuring that all her learners received the utmost quality education. P4 shared that throughout his academic journey, he had consistently demonstrated proficiency in utilizing a wide range of digital tools, thereby significantly enhancing his learning experience in both virtual and physical classroom settings. These technologies are essential for improving the learning experience by facilitating more involvement and participation. Nevertheless, due to the existing limitations imposed by social distancing and safety norms, the task of tailoring education to the unique needs of individual students has grown progressively more difficult. Typically, he experienced work fatigue on a regular basis. P7 added that as an educator amidst a pandemic, she understood that maintaining patience is crucial. Every student is responding to this scenario in a distinct manner, and it is crucial to acknowledge and account for these individual differences. She strived to meet their requirements and offer assistance wherever feasible.

Nevertheless, he had occasionally have difficulties in efficiently organizing his time. He efficiently managed numerous obligations and activities, ensuring that he prioritized and accomplished them promptly while maintaining the high quality of his teaching. Occasionally, he further experienced stress as a result of deadlines and a significant amount of work. This discovery is connected to Spitzer's (2022) research, which indicates that several COVID-19 health and safety requirements hindered the effectiveness of education. While face masks are necessary for in-person teaching, they may impede social and linguistic communication between students and professors. Spitzer examines the advantages and disadvantages of communicating while wearing a face mask, which has the ability to absorb higher frequencies and diminish visual lip cues. Finally, the conversation lacks a clear objective. Speaking continuously while wearing a face mask might lead to voice fatigue as it necessitates extra exertion to communicate. It could result in mental exhaustion and subsequent weariness. Ribeiro et al. (2020) conducted a comparative analysis of the impact of wearing a face mask in a working group as opposed to a vital activities group. The utilization of the face mask resulted in symptoms such as weariness, diminished vocal abilities, vocal fatigue, and abnormalities in the voice. Professionals who wear face masks experience detrimental effects on their vocal tract when they try to speak well while synchronizing their breathing and speaking. This leads to vocal fatigue, which is linked to cognitive tiredness. Mental tiredness leads to fatigue and a feeling of exertion. Fatigue is also influenced by the level of professional and personal stress experienced by instructors. Further, this major theme generated sub-themes relating to the other challenges huddled by teachers in public schools. These sub themes are multiple workloads, worries getting sick and the academic problems. These factors are considered the reason why teachers felt chal-

lenged in the classroom. Further, these themes are specifically discussed in the following.

3.1.4. Multiple workloads—This theme focuses on the occurrence of teacher burnout, which refers to a condition when educators face a reduced ability to fulfill their duties effectively due to an excessive load of responsibilities and related sources of stress. Teacher burnout refers to a condition of physical, emotional, and attitudinal weariness or depletion, marked by a feeling of discomfort and reduced satisfaction in the process of teaching. When educators experience burnout, they may develop negative attitudes towards their students, which can reduce their effectiveness in teaching. If a teacher encounters burnout, the educational system may be adversely affected since this crucial element may no longer deliver its complete advantages. Work tiredness in teachers can result in apathy and reluctance to participate in all student activities, perhaps leading to inadequate fulfillment of the requirements of children with special needs. The person has concerns about the heavy workload of teachers in public schools and suggests that the government should provide more time to help with lesson planning, assessing student work, calculating grades, and tracking student progress. In the end, the whole health and psychological state of educators is affected. P7 stressed that her teaching experience was hard due to the need to effectively handle various learning paces, classroom capacity, time constraints, and technological integration. Implementation of social distancing protocols resulted in a decrease in classroom capacity, necessitating her to oversee a greater number of classes with a smaller student population. The increased burden made it more challenging to efficiently allocate her time. Incorporating technology into in-person instruction posed an additional difficulty, especially for educators who lacked proficiency in using technology. The number of tasks increased twofold, resulting in a corresponding doubling of stress

levels. P9 added that Implementing interactive tasks while adhering to social distance protocols proved to be a demanding endeavor that necessitated considerable ingenuity and strategic preparation. As an educator, she must simultaneously take into account several responsibilities and workloads. P10 concluded that teaching has unique difficulties. A significant obstacle is in managing pupils who encountered home-based distractions that impede their ability to concentrate on their studies. Furthermore, effectively organizing storage space in the classroom to accommodate the learning resources of each student was also a formidable task. Indeed, managing professional development alongside teaching obligations can be challenging. This result is related to the notion that teachers are burdened with preparing modules, facilitating online sessions, and attending schools for a small number of in-person classes, a triple load. As COVID-19 incidents have dropped, the administration is now optimistic about its plan to progressively introduce face-to-face instruction in some schools around the country. Face-to-face instruction and physically reporting on location, however, pose substantial challenges for some teachers and their pupils. Teachers have begun conducting sessions in their houses two years ago. Teachers were puzzled by the new working environment in the middle of the ongoing epidemic when the Department of Education (DepEd) introduced limited face-to-face classes and forced teachers to be present every day. As a response, DepEd issued Memorandum No. 29 or the Work Arrangements in the Department of Education During the Imposition of Alert Level 1 System for COVID 19 Response in April of this year, mandating 100 percent onsite reporting of teaching and non-teaching personnel in areas subject to the most lax alert status. The government has begun implementing limited face-to-face training, in addition to modular and online programs. In addition to attempting to overcome the hurdles and challenges caused by

the Philippines' sluggish transition to limited face-to-face classes, these teachers are urging that the government provide more assistance and recognize their struggles. As instructors continued to practice their three teaching methods, they expressed hope that the government would investigate their true and difficult position.

3.1.5. Worries getting sick—The utilization of face masks has been shown to be effective in mitigating the transmission of CoVid-19, particularly given the potential for asymptomatic individuals to spread the virus. The act of covering the lower half of the face has been found to diminish the capacity for communication, interpretation, and emulation of the facial expressions of individuals with whom we engage. The recognition of positive emotions tends to decrease, while negative emotions tend to be intensified. The reduction of emotional mimicry, contagion, and overall emotionality can have a negative impact on the bonding between teachers and learners, group cohesion, and learning outcomes, as emotions play a significant role in driving the learning process. It is imperative to thoroughly evaluate and elucidate that everyone in schools during this time is afraid to get sick or any illness. That is why in the study, the fear to get sick was considered as a challenge that teachers faced. P1 and P3 shared the same thoughts. They mentioned the following: in a conventional classroom, teachers encountered numerous challenges that posed difficulties. Several students encountered difficulties in adapting, while others expressed concerns over their health, and a few struggled to keep pace with the academic demands. The arrangement of the classroom posed a challenge as we had to maintain a considerable physical distance from one another and diligently sanitize all surfaces. As the educator, they had to exert additional effort to alleviate their students' concerns on the current circumstances. It was challenging to devise innovative teaching meth-

ods that would both engage students and ensure their safety. The other participant also mentioned that came across learners who expressed apprehension regarding the potential health hazards linked to in-person classes. The presence of this anxiety could have a detrimental impact on their ability to concentrate and actively engage in classroom activities, posing a significant problem for me as an educator. Furthermore, ensuring regular sanitization of the classroom and learning materials was a logistical difficulty. As individuals who offered emotional assistance to students amidst these trying circumstances, teachers occasionally found it challenging to maintain a balance with their teaching obligations. All these posed difficulties. With this, the UNICEF which is assisting the Departments of Education and Health in the Philippines to implemented safe, voluntary, and phased re-opening of face to face classes in schools in low-risk areas. Low-risk regions are municipalities with a negative two-week growth rate and fewer than one COVID-19 case per 100,000 residents. To ensure the safety of children attending in-person classes, all feasible steps must be taken to prevent the spread of viruses in schools, including: Mask, face shield, and other PPE policies for teachers, school staff, and students must adhere to national and local regulations. Improved hygiene practices and handwashing facilities, frequent cleaning of common surfaces and items, adequate and appropriate ventilation, cohorting and rotating physical presence to preserve physical separation and small groupings, mechanisms for communicating with parents and teachers, and establishing criteria and mandated processes for the temporary closure of schools in the event of a COVID-19 pandemic in the region. These efforts eased the burden of everyone in school to think about getting sick.

3.1.6. Academic problems—The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in substantial disruptions to education systems, specifically affecting the most susceptible learners. This has led to

the worsening of pre-existing disparities, which might have significant and long-lasting effects. The quick requires prompt actions to address educational shortcomings and provide smooth and uninterrupted academic advancement for all students. In the near future, it will be crucial for educational systems to strengthen the ability of learners to bounce back from challenges by providing favorable circumstances that provide individuals with the essential skills to reach their full potential. The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines has introduced distance learning modalities in response to the COVID-19 epidemic to ensure uninterrupted learning. The Department of Education (DepEd) recognizes the challenges in offering alternate learning modalities to a substantial portion of elementary and secondary students. Due to the challenges posed by distance learning and the unequal distribution of resources, students from marginalized backgrounds who are already struggling academically may face a further widening of the achievement gap. Before the epidemic, the Philippines' subpar performance in regional and worldwide assessments of academic attainment had raised worries about the quality of basic education in the country. The Department of Education (DepEd) is actively investigating innovative strategies to address the difficulties in education caused by the pandemic, and to achieve the required learning results when students transition to in-person classrooms. P4 and P6 shared that learning gaps and academic problems are evident among the learning outputs and behavioral outcomes among the students. They observed that the transition to online learning has resulted in some knowledge deficiencies among some of the stu-

dents. Identifying and addressing these gaps proved to be difficult when they were in a face-to-face scenario. Evaluating the pupils' comprehension and advancement Further, effectively managing classroom conduct while adhering to social distance protocols proved challenging, but the task of improving learners' academic performance was much more arduous. The presence of academic gaps is apparent and conspicuous according to the participants. This scenario is supported by the findings of UNICEF (2022) that teachers encountered unique classroom issues as a result of the longer distance education. Lack of in-person peer interaction has a significant impact on the emotional and cognitive development of children. The lost opportunity for immediate teacher-learner interaction on the lessons retards the development of the learner's competencies and impairs the quality of learning. The ability of children to read, write, and perform basic mathematics, as well as the skills they need to thrive in the twenty-first century economy, have dropped. Less likely are children to return to school the longer they remain missing. Children who are not in school are more likely to engage in child labor, child marriage, and teen pregnancy. Their physical and emotional health, development, safety, and well-being are at risk. More time spent online and in front of a screen has increased the probability of online hostility and abuse. They are more susceptible to domestic abuse, gender-based violence, including sexual exploitation and child marriage, and child labor, especially in the context of the epidemic. Mental health, psychological support, and health and nutrition services are lacking in schools.

3.2. *Coping mechanisms of kinder teachers in the instructional challenges encountered in the new face-to-face classes mode*—The second research objective of this study focuses on

the coping mechanisms of public kinder teachers on the challenges they experienced in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in schools. Figure four shows the summary of

Fig. 3. The instructional challenges of elementary school teachers in the new face-to-face classes mode

their coping strategies. As seen in Figure 4, the coping strategies of teacher researchers are divided into two (2) major themes. These are creating personality improvement interventions

3.2.1. Creating personality improvement interventions—Consistently implementing and utilizing a well-designed learning plan or intervention program throughout the school is considered the most effective strategy to address learning challenges among kids. A school's commitment to creating a safe, empathetic, and inclusive learning environment that meets the needs of all students is crucial in the current circumstances. The school's implementation of a strategy to prevent and address learning setbacks and difficulties may involve various elements, including behavior programs, forms, interaction philosophies, curriculum, and core protocols. Effective learning programs or curricula often include a comprehensive plan of knowledge and competencies that all students must achieve. These programs require the participation and support of the entire school community. Specialized guidance designed to meet the unique needs of students engaged in educational settings. Undoubtedly, it is imperative for schools to implement a well-defined consistent intervention approach to address academic concerns. The participants of this study presented their ideas as to how they coped with some difficulties or challenges they experienced. P9 mentioned her extensive collaboration with fellow educators, engaging in the exchange of instructional materials and methodologies. This partnership enabled her to manage the hurdles effectively and assures that no individual is working independently. As a collective, teachers implemented classroom-based intervention programs alongside their fellow educators. P6 added that he placed a high importance on both his own mental well-being and that of his students. He integrated mindfulness practices into

and continuous improvement in the new normal. These summarized the coping strategies of the teachers as they deal with the challenges of the current research circumstances.

the classroom and seek assistance as necessary. P9 finally shared that she cultivated the virtue of patience, recognizing that each individual is traversing unfamiliar and unexplored terrain. He provided himself and his pupils leniency as they adapt to the new standard. He dedicated time to familiarize himself with each learner and provide personalized treatments based on their specific needs. The discovery pertains to the extrapolation of Sique-Bisnar's (2022) research, emphasizing the imperative for educational institutions to devise a recovery response strategy. An essential initiative highlighted by UNESCO, UNICEF, and the World Bank in their Mission: Recovering Education 2021 campaign is the expansion of physical educational institutions. Furthermore, the development of recovery response strategies can assist schools in addressing and resolving learning disparities. The DepEd declared in March of this year its intention to build a framework for school rehabilitation as part of its post-pandemic initiatives to assist schools. In the future, educational institutions will benefit from these recovery response plans, which may involve activities such as systematic student monitoring and evaluation, as well as the incorporation of diverse on-site and digital learning technologies and instructional approaches. Undoubtedly, it is imperative for teachers to incorporate remedial. It is advisable for schools to give priority to remedial education starting from the present academic year to tackle the achievement gaps resulting from the time limitations imposed by the pandemic. Aside from regular academic instruction, it is important to take into account the availability of tutoring services. The results of remedial learning programs can be utilized to assess the

reading and numeracy abilities of individual students, enabling schools to adapt their current teaching practices to better meet the needs of their pupils.

3.2.2. Continuous Improvement—The Covid-19 pandemic has brought about numerous difficulties, especially in the field of education, where the predominant mode of learning has transitioned to online engagement and distant education as the prevalent standard. As a result of enforcing health rules that require maintaining physical distance, opportunities for direct interaction and personal engagement are limited. Teacher professional development (TPD) is the merging of good practices and strategies that enables educators to cultivate their own professional vision. The study suggests that Teacher Professional Development (TPD) is a way for educators to enhance and improve their knowledge and skills, and promote their professional growth, considering that teaching is an ongoing learning activity. Before the Covid-19 pandemic, TPD programs consisted of many efforts that targeted content, pedagogy, technology, action learning, graduate studies, leadership and management, and action research. During the epidemic, educators were given chances to engage in online seminars and educational activities focused on remote teaching, technology skills, and mental health. Regardless of their age and tenure, educators maintain a growth-oriented mindset focused on improving their professional abilities and increasing their effectiveness in teaching. The individual aims to undergo a process of unlearning obsolete knowledge and obtaining new knowledge and abilities. This is driven by a motivation to guarantee that their pupils possess the knowledge and abilities that are pertinent to their present and future requirements. P1 shared that in order to facilitate the success of in-person classes, she undertook a multitude of tasks. She attended a training session to acquire knowledge on novel pedagogical approaches suitable for in-person instruction. She collaborated with fellow educators to generate innovative ideas. She remained receptive to change, engaged in frequent communication with parents and students, prioritized self-care, utilized technology, experimented with diverse teaching methods, and demonstrated patience and empathy. These factors facilitated her effective teaching despite the challenges encountered. P3 explained that she utilized technology to improve learning experiences, even in a traditional classroom context. Utilizing digital tools enabled her to deliver captivating and dynamic classes, effectively bridging the divide between students participating online and those attending in person. She participated in many educational workshops as a means of consistently enhancing my skills as an educator. P4 added that he was dedicated to ongoing education and the enhancement of his professional skills. By remaining informed about the most recent teaching methodologies and safety protocols, he was capable of efficiently overseeing his classes. This finding is supported by the notions of Sigue-Bisnar (2022) that DepEd may offer help to educators. To prepare their students for Education 4.0 in the digital age, teachers must also be technologically savvy. In addition to ensuring that faculty members receive regular and continuous learning opportunities and skill development aimed at enhancing their capacity to give effective in-person and virtual instruction, schools are also responsible for guaranteeing this. Unquestionably, private educational institutions must raise their expenditures on digital tools that faculty members must be adept with. Further, as we gradually adjust to the new normal and move toward recovery from the terrible consequences of the epidemic, schools must remember that innovation is the way to go. Even though it is

Fig. 4. Coping mechanisms of elementary school teachers in the instructional challenges encountered in the new face-to-face classes mode

improbable that another pandemic of the magnitude of the COVID-19 pandemic will ever hit the entire planet, it is best to be prepared. Schools may accomplish this by fostering a creative mindset and going above and beyond to support teachers and students (Sigue-Bisnar, 2022).

3.3. Educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences and challenges of kindergarten teachers—The last research objective of this study focuses on the insights or lessons learned by public elementary school teachers in the new mode of face-to-face classes in schools. Figure five (5) shows the summary of insights and lessons learned. Based on the experiences and challenges of the kindergarten teachers in public elementary schools, they had their respective insights to further improve their experiences in the new normal. These insights were some of the personal thoughts of the participants that they deemed significant in under-

standing their real situations in schools. As seen in Figure 5, the insights of the participants are divided into three major themes. These are work-life balance, obeying safety protocols and the importance of hybrid learning. These summarized the insights of the teachers based on their experiences in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in schools including the challenges and coping mechanisms. Based on their responses, although they experienced ups and downs in the process, still their insights have always reminded them of the lessons and things that they learned which made them more equipped and competent as new normal classroom teachers amidst the pandemic.

3.3.1. *Work life balance*—Finding a way to attain work-life equilibrium as an educator is an immense obstacle. Teachers choose their job with the aspiration of making a significant impact on students' lives. However, they frequently encounter challenges and confront seemingly insurmountable expectations. Striking a balance between professional success and maintaining a healthy personal life can enable educators to cultivate a fulfilling, content, and physically sound professional journey. As educators, it is common to become preoccupied with minor details: the lesson plan that did not meet our expectations, the evaluation that need adjustment, the email that must be sent today. However, in certain occasions, it is necessary to relinquish control and allow things to unfold naturally. The earth's axial stability will not be compromised by your failure to compose the aforementioned email or incorporate the supplementary lecture on commas into the curriculum this evening. Although we do our utmost effort, it is imperative to acknowledge that certain circumstances lie outside our influence. Inhale deeply and exhale, releasing the breath. In the study, teachers are mastering the art of attaining work-life equilibrium as an educator, particularly at the initial stages of one's career as their way of coping up with the challenges. For them, it is crucial for survival. Implementing work-life balance tactics can guarantee that their teaching profession is not only influential, but also robust and enduring. P2 shared that he learned to recognize the significance of resilience during this pandemic. As an educator, he encountered various modifications and obstacles, yet he acquired the resilience to persevere and consistently deliver high-quality instruction to his pupils. It was important to achieve a harmonious equilibrium between personal and professional commitments. P3 expressed that she

acquired an understanding of the importance of adaptability in instructional techniques. The transition to in-person classes during the pandemic has underscored the necessity of adapting her approaches in accordance with the present circumstances. She adjusted her teaching methods to include safety precautions and have found strategies to effectively engage kids in a classroom where social distancing is required. Moreover, by being adaptable, teachers are more likely to achieve equilibrium between our work and personal spheres. P10 added that preserving an optimistic outlook and achieving equilibrium between work and personal life had been crucial in effectively managing the difficulties posed by the pandemic. By directing teachers' attention towards the advancements they are achieving, rather than the obstacles they faced, he personally managed everything. This finding is related to Rapoport and Bailyn' reports in their 1996 study in the Ford Foundation, they highlighted that the division between work and family life has persisted since the Industrial Revolution and continues to be prevalent today, despite not accurately representing the lifestyles of most individuals. The business sector has implemented several programs and policies to tackle work-family conflicts, aiming to cater to individual family requirements. However, these initiatives do not alter the fundamental notion that employees' professional and personal lives are distinct and in conflict with each other. Work-family research has traditionally been influenced by the role stress hypothesis, which focuses on the negative aspects of the work-family connection. In recent times, there has been a shift in focus towards studying the beneficial interplay between work and life roles balance, as well as roles outside of work and home domains. Scholars have begun to discuss the significance of achieving work-life balance (Jones et al., 2019).

3.3.2. *Obedience to safety protocols*—

Individuals nationwide have heightened their safety measures in response to the initial onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. It is imperative to persist in implementing these safety precautions until the virus is effectively managed and a suitable vaccine is developed to provide universal protection against its transmission. Despite teachers acknowledging the potential issue of asphyxia caused by wearing masks, they adhere to safety measures in schools and highlight the necessity of mask-wearing to students. The participants emphasized the significance of consistently adhering to the guidelines as a habitual practice. The participants of this study had given their respective insights in the implementation of face-to-face classes. P1 mentioned that conducting in-person classes within the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the significance of adaptability and perseverance. Adapting to novel teaching methods, adhering to health protocols, and ensuring the well-being of children posed significant challenges. However, these obstacles facilitated her personal development and acquisition of knowledge, necessitating the exploration of innovative methods to engage and educate her students. It was crucial to comprehend the individual needs of each pupil. The pandemic has prompted me to see the significance of teaching and the necessity of being resilient and flexible in adhering to the

government's safety procedures. P8 shared that ensuring his personal physical and mental well-being had been essential for him to carry out his duties as a teacher proficiently. Amidst the challenges of instructing during a pandemic, he came to understand the need of prioritizing self-care. It was imperative that teachers adhere to the health protocols. The finding is related to the conceptualizations of Swartz (2021) states that school personnel must adhere to the COVID-19 safety requirements. According to the most recent CDC standards, everyone should wear a mask and workstations should always be at least three feet apart. Students should maintain a six-foot distance while not wearing masks, such as during lunch. Vaccinations are recommended but not necessary; currently, they are only administered to children 12 years of age and older. There is a current push for the majority of students to return to educational institutions across the nation, ideally with standard class sizes. If students are seated in rows in their classrooms, the possibilities of group work may be limited. During small-group instruction, it will be vital to ensure proper ventilation, and teachers will need to consider student safety while enabling cooperation or sharing of resources. Everyone must be reminded on the learning hat following protocols can make schools better and safer.

3.3.3. The importance of hybrid learning— The impact of digitalization on education was already evident before the COVID-19 pandemic due to the widespread adoption of online learning. Nevertheless, the lockdowns caused by the pandemic have made this technique widely popular, except in cases where the digital divide creates obstacles, therefore requiring students to engage in remote learning. After the first surge of the pandemic, the educational sector faced the challenge of getting ready for the new academic year. Blended learning has be-

come a steadfast commitment for the current and future of education. The study focused on instructing participants about the significance of blended learning. Blended learning has various advantages, such as improved student motivation and achievement, heightened engagement, independent learning, and collaboration. Additionally, it enables innovative forms of communication between teachers and students, provides increased adaptability, and promotes the growth of digital literacy and the acquisition of digital competencies. As part of their in-

Fig. 5. Educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences and challenges of kinder teachers

sights, P1 shared that DepEd must ensure that all teachers receive comprehensive training to effectively manage the difficulties associated with in-person classes under the current circumstances. This encompasses instruction on safety standards, administration of a hybrid classroom, and provision of emotional assistance to pupils. P2 expressed that classrooms must to be furnished with essential resources to facilitate efficient instruction in the current circumstances. This encompasses disinfection provisions, individualized sets of educational resources for students, and technological resources for blended learning. P8 added that DepEd should offer teachers opportunities to augment their expertise and expand their knowledge. These methods may include webinars, workshops, or the provision of educational resources. There is a possibility that schools would prioritize hybrid

learning and other alternative learning methods in order to provide continuous education. The result is related to the findings of Singh (2017) that through hybrid and blended training, students can experience face-to-face and online learning, as well as scheduled and self-paced coursework. This style of instruction has the potential to become the norm because it allows teachers to reinvent and modify content, especially in fields where instructors have struggled to provide students with an engaging online learning experience. Change is accompanied by questions in every field. As we prepare to teach in a post-vaccine and post-pandemic world, there is a clear need for research demonstrating the experiences of teachers, the effectiveness of blended and hybrid instruction, and how teachers might design classrooms to make it a viable option for the present and future.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the lived experiences, challenges encountered, coping mechanisms and insights of kinder teachers on their instructional challenges in the full implementation of face-to-face classes in public elementary schools. The participants were coming from Arakan, West District, Division of Cotabato, DepEd Region XII. In order to achieve the research goals, I utilized a qualitative phenomenological methodology that involved topic analysis. In accordance with Cresswell's (2006) recommendations, open-ended interview queries were utilized to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, I prompted the individuals I interviewed to openly and clearly articulate their personal definition or understanding of the issue being studied, namely the experiences of elementary school teachers instructions in carrying out in-person classes at schools.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the teacher participants, the following themes were revealed. The lived experiences of kinder teachers in the full implementation of face-to-face classes can be summed up in (3) major themes. These are: concretizing the learners' socialization skills, considering health protocols and hurdling work stress. There were three sub-themes that emerged from the challenges or

work fatigue by the participants. These are multiple workloads, worries getting sick and the academic problems. The two coping mechanisms of teachers as participants in the challenges they experienced were creating personal-ity improvement interventions and continuous improvement in the new normal. The three educational management insights drawn from the participants were work-life balance, obeying safety protocols and the importance of hybrid learning.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The experiences of kinder teachers who fully implemented face-to-face sessions can be described as a pioneering effort to reintroduce the traditional classroom setup, but with enhancements and modifications to ensure the delivery of high-quality educational experiences to students. These ideas might be employed to define their actual experiences in educational institutions. The inclusion of in-person sessions in these programs was facilitated through the involvement and collaboration of the public-school teachers. They acted as the main catalyst or the forefront pioneers in the subject of education. Educators prioritize the cultivation of learners' interpersonal skills as a crucial attribute that teachers must foster. Currently, in-

structors are providing instruction or delivering courses in situations characterized by scarce resources, while also facing the challenges of job-related stress in the current circumstances. The study examined the specific difficulties and challenges resulting from occupational stress and burnout, which were analyzed and connected to the participants' learning stations. Consequently, there are noticeable deficiencies in knowledge acquisition among pupils, teachers are subjected to increased stress due to large extra responsibilities, and the efficiency of school activities and processes is hindered by stringent protocols and procedures. Teachers utilized the implementation of rehabilitation programs to address emotional, academic, and holistic needs of learners and provided professional development training for teachers within the context of the

new normal. These strategies were employed to cope with the challenges faced by teachers. Teachers employed these coping methods as a way to deal with the challenges they encountered. Both of these coping strategies were facilitated by the transition and adjustment to the current state of affairs. The study revealed three crucial lessons for educational management: the importance of cultivating work-life balance, the value of integrated learning, and the necessity of strictly adhering to safety regulations. The study's findings illuminate the diverse perspec-

tives of public elementary school teachers as they navigate their management techniques in the teaching and learning processes throughout the new normal. The study examined the behaviors and responses of the educators. The insights gained from structured interviews can be valuable for educators and scholars who are interested in studying similar phenomena. The coping skills employed by participants can serve as a valuable resource for individuals facing similar circumstances.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the results are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. The Department of Education may consider the revision of its guidelines or rules in order to enhance the effectiveness of face-to-face classes as a method and mechanism in schools during the new normal. The government, particularly the health agencies, may assess the activities of educators and students in schools where Covid-19 protocols impede the effectiveness of teaching and learning. They may develop secure and health-conscious procedures for all individuals involved in the educational processes at school. Division authorities, Dis-

trict Supervisors, School administrators, and heads may motivate and assist their teachers by evaluating their workloads and endorsing their endeavors to tackle educational deficiencies in schools. Additionally, they can establish a comprehensive initiative or initiative to enhance the skills and expertise of teachers, enabling them to effectively and efficiently carry out both in-person classes and alternative teaching methods in educational institutions. Schools and teachers may create activities and contextualized remediation programs for the learners to minimize or eradicate learning gaps. Future researchers may embark on the same research with different participants, places, and schools. Other avenues not scrutinized in this research may also be explored.

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